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APPLICATION OF LS-SVM METHOD IN PROBABILISTIC STABILITY ANALYSIS OF SATURATED SOIL SLOPES

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ABSTRACT

To assess the stability of a soil slope considering uncertainty in soil characteristics (C , Φ), it is necessary to conduct repeated calculations to determine both the Factor of Safety (FS) and the Probability of Failure (PF). The absence of analytical solutions leads researchers to use surrogate approaches of probabilistic modeling. This study aims to assess the PF and FS of a saturated soil slope using one of the Machine Learning (ML) method subsets, the regression Least Squares Support Vector Machine (LS-SVM). The results are compared to those obtained from the Limit Equilibrium Method (LEM) to compare the accuracy of LS-SVM. According to the FS-PF plot, it is concluded that LS-SVM is a reliable tool for determining the stability of a multi-layered saturated soil slope, which significantly improves computational efficiency. Furthermore, since predicting FS and PF from field data requires fewer data points, it will result in significant time and cost savings. However, to avoid false predictions, limitations must be removed, for instance, each layer should be included in the analysis within its probabilistic distribution, so using this method is more efficacious in clay soils where there are values for cohesion, unlike sands ($c = 0$). This helps training data to be prepared well and to prevent misprediction in local failures. In addition, training data are debated in terms of the percentage employed. Furthermore, showing the importance of dataset scattering is concluded that adopting data with uniform distributions plays a crucial role in preparing training data sets and consequently, in having a better prediction of the possible slope failures.

keywords: LS-SVM, Uncertainty, Machine Learning, Latin Hypercube Simulation, Probabilistic Stability

SECTION 1: INTRODUCTION

To evaluate the Factor of Safety (FS) in soil slopes, standard methods such as Finite Element Method (FEM), Limit Equilibrium Method (LEM), and Strength Reduction Method (SRM) are used. Among them, LEM and SRM are also employed in probabilistic modeling. In the deterministic method, FS is assessed based on the constant characteristics of soil structure. In this way, the most essential issue is to find the critical surface. FS is determined through trial and error or optimization methods to address this. (Xue and Gavin 2007). Since failure to identify the most critical slip in slopes with several failure surfaces could lead to an unsafe and high-risk design (Griffiths et al. 2012), taking advantage of a robust algorithm is vital to examine the most critical surfaces. However, both LEM and FEM methods require fundamental knowledge about slope failure mechanisms, complex calculations, and numerical codes that should be involved (Duncan 1996). In probabilistic approaches, variables perform based on their statistical distributions to consider the uncertainties in evaluating a slope's reliability. Moreover, stability is assessed through the Probability of Failure (PF) and Factor of Safety (FS). The crucial point is that slopes with identical FS may have different levels of PF because the PF is affected by uncertainty in soil characteristics, laboratory testing, and the selection of soil parameters. Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods in probabilistic modeling of soil slopes have become more common in recent years. To consider the impact of soil variables like cohesion and frictional angle (C , Φ) and their effects on FS and PF of the multilayer slopes analysis, the data training, data testing, and kernel functions play crucial roles in ML approaches. Various methods such as Neural Network (NN) (Goh and Kulhawy 2003; Sakellariou and Ferentinou 2005, Lü et al. 2012, Alidadi and Pezeshk 2024), Gaussian Process (GP) (Pal and Deswal

2010; Kang et al. 2015), SVM, and LS-SVM have proven that if trained well, are powerful tools in probabilistic slope stability analysis. (Zhao 2008; Samui et al. 2013; Kang and Li 2016) This research looks for an alternative method for computing PF and FS with a more straightforward process using ML techniques.

SECTION 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

The effectiveness of ML methods in predicting soil slope failures has been discussed in the last decade. Kang et al. 2015 run a probabilistic analysis using the Gaussian Process (GP) to discover the possibility of failure in soil slopes using five case studies. The outputs indicated that employing GP ends up in an increase in computational efficiency while using less input data. Hoang and Pham (2016) used a least-square support vector classification method to predict the potential of failure through 168 individual cases of soil slopes. They optimized the model using a Firefly Algorithm, as well. The outcome indicated a 4% increase in computational accuracy compared to the other traditional numerical methods. In another study, Youssef and Pourghasemi (2021) compared seven ML models predicting potential landslides at Abha Basin, Asir Region, Saudi Arabia. They recognized twelve variable indices like the angle of slope, altitude, and vegetation index, leaving 70% of data for training and 30% for testing. The outcomes showed that Random Forest (RF) and Linear Discriminant Analysis outperformed compared to other methods. Hakim et al. (2022) assessed the potential landslides utilizing Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Grey Wolf (GW) optimization techniques with eighteen variables indices. They summarized that using optimization methods in ML modeling has a vital impact on preparing hyperparameters, leading to increase in computational accuracy. In the following, some comparisons between these methods are presented:

- For an alternative model with the best training data, predicting new data with SVM and LS-SVM presents better performance against GP. Because GP includes vectors and matrix, while SVM and LS-SVM involve vector multiplication. As a result, SVM and LS-SVM are further suitable for MCS, where prediction data is used.
- Owing to quadratic programming, SVM has higher computational difficulty; furthermore, three statements (such as error insensitive zone, capacity factor, and kernel parameter) are involved in SVM tuning. In this situation, the evaluation of these parameters is challenging work. (Vapnik 2000; Samui 2008)
- In Neural Network and Gaussian Process, the possibility of misreporting at local minimums increases if training data is not selected appropriately. (Gori and Tesi 1992; Rasmussen and Williams 2005) However, this problem does not make any problem in SVM or LS-SVM methods. (Vapnik 2000; Bennett and Campbell 2000; Suykens and Vandewalle 1999)

The content of LS-SVM Regression is discussed in section 3; then, a multigure soil slope is modeled to compare the results of LEM and LS-SVM. After that, the data generation procedure is discussed in section 5. The size of training data is debated in section 6. The robustness of LS-SVM in computing PF is shown in section 7. Finally, the summary and conclusion are presented in sections 8 and 9.

SECTION 3: BASICS OF LS-SVM REGRESSION

LS-SVM originally was defined by the statistical learning theory. (Goh 2007; Maalouf et al. 2008) This paper has tried to overcome the deficiencies of SVM in soil slope failure prediction utilizing LS-SVM. This method exerts linear least-squares as an alternative to a quadratic optimization program, (Suykens et al. 2002a) based on regularization networks and the Gaussian process. LS-SVM is expressed as a boosted SVM, which if combined with a linear kernel or Radial Basis Function (RBF) significantly increases the computational efficiency in evaluating probabilistic soil slope stability. The success of this method directly depends on the quality of the pre-established sampled datasets, as well as their quantity. As a

result, determining the training datasets and hyper-parameters is the key. On the other hand, to create a simpler cost function, a highly nonlinear function is transformed into a linear one by regression analysis. In the end, the accuracy of LS-SVM is approximated by comparing the outputs of estimated and testing datasets. Splitting datasets based on a certain percentage of training and testing data is another key point. Each training data contains an output value (FS), and several input variables (γ , C , Φ). In the following, the structure of LS-SVM has been presented. Consider a training dataset included N points, $\{x_i, y_i\}$, while the input datasets are $x_i \in R^N$, and output datasets are $y_i \in R$. Φ and R form an N -dimensional and One-dimensional vector space, respectively. To describe an optimization model, the feature space is as follow:

$$\text{Minimize Function: } J = -\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{w}^T \Phi + \frac{\gamma}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N e_i^2 \quad [1]$$

$$= \mathbf{w}^T (\Phi(x_i) + \mathbf{b} + e_i), \quad i = (1, \dots, N) \quad [2]$$

In which, J = cost function including fitting error e_i ; γ = positive constant which present the regularization term; \mathbf{w} = tunable weight vector ($\mathbf{w} \in R^n$); and b reflects the bias phrase ($\mathbf{b} \in R$). Particularly, $\Phi(\cdot)$ as a nonlinear function transmits the primitive input dataset \mathbf{x}_i to a feature space with a higher dimension. Then it turns a nonlinear objective function into a linear function to consider a regression analysis. This act culminates in a simplified cost function. See Eqs. 1 and 2 and Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Transformation to feature space from input space (After Ji et al.,

2017). LS-SVM calculates the following formulation in the primal weight space:

$$= \mathbf{w}^T \Phi(x) + b \quad [3]$$

To compute weight vector (\mathbf{w}), the least-square vectors of SVM is built-in so-called dual space with the help of Lagrange, which is shown as follow:

$$= - \sum \alpha_i \{ [\mathbf{w}^T \Phi(x_i) + \mathbf{b} + e_i] - y_i \} \quad [4]$$

In this equation, values of Lagrange Multipliers $\alpha \in R$ and constitute support vector α . Eventually, the optimization problem is solved in Eq.5 in which N . The solutions of these linear equations are the support vector (α), as well as bias term (b) of Eq.6 According to Suykens et al. (2002b).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial w} = 0; \quad w = \boldsymbol{\alpha}^T \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x_i) \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial b} = 0; \quad \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i = 0 \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial e_i} = 0; \quad \alpha_i = \gamma e_i \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \alpha_i} = 0; \quad w^T \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x_i) + e_i - y_i = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad [5]$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{1}v^T \\ \mathbf{1}v & \boldsymbol{\Omega} + \frac{1}{\gamma}\mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b \\ \boldsymbol{\alpha} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \mathbf{y} \end{bmatrix} \quad [6]$$

In Eq.6, $\mathbf{1}v = [1, \dots, 1]$; $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = [\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_N]$; $\mathbf{y} = [y_1, \dots, y_N]$ respectively. Besides, $\boldsymbol{\Omega} =$ matrix of $\Omega_{ij} = \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x_i)^T \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x_j)$, while $i, j = 1$ to N . Moreover, kernel function represents mapping function $\boldsymbol{\varphi}(\cdot)$, according to Mercer's clause:

$$K(x_i, x_j) = \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x_i)^T \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x_j) \quad i, j = 1, \dots, N \quad [7]$$

Eventually, The LS-SVM mechanism works as follow to compute for predictor function:

$$Y_{(x)} = \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i K(x, x_i) + b \quad [8]$$

Another principal part of LS-SVM is hyper-parameters which includes the kernel constant (σ) and the regularization constant (γ). These coefficients are trained through trial and error to obtain optimization solutions. As mentioned earlier, FS is a function of geotechnical parameters that define the state of stability involving unit weight, soil strength parameters, and geometries. In this study, the cohesion, internal friction angle, and unit weight are used probabilistically to model the FS and PF. Eventually, the LS-SVM function is as follow:

$$FS = LSSVM_{(x)} = LSSVM_{(x_1, \dots, x_n)} \quad [9]$$

According to the estimated datasets of the LS-SVM model, PF will be computed. As a result, for n number of the Estimated dataset, the PF is formulated by:

$$P_f = \frac{n' [LSSVM_{(x_1, \dots, x_n)} < 1]}{n} \quad [10]$$

In which $n' [LSSVM_{(x_1, \dots, x_n)} < 1] =$ number of LHS results that are less than one (Ji et al. 2017). As a surrogate model, the LS-SVM contains nine soil characteristics with uniform distributions in cohesion, and frictional angle. The training samples for LS-SVM evaluation are produced according to the LEM and circular slip surface method.

SECTION 4: EXAMPLE OF MULTI-LAYERED SATURATED SOIL SLOPE

To verify the validity of the LS-SVM model in predicting failure surfaces, a typical slope of the association for computer-aided design (ACADS) by Giam and Donald (1989) has been used (Slide 6.0 software). For slope profile and soil properties, see Fig. 2 and Table 1. The first layer consists of sand, and the following two layers contain saturated clay. The slope profile has been designed by the Spencer method to determine the critical failure surfaces under probabilistic modeling with $N= 30,000$ Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS). The analysis shows that PF is 16.203% for minimum FS =1.198 at the mean value point, in which cohesion and frictional angle have been distributed uniformly. PF is 5.45% for critical FS = 1.162 under the normal distribution. These differences are influential in the LS-SVM model.

Fig. 2. Slope profile of multi-layered saturated soil slope

Table 1. Soil properties of the first layer

Statement	Cohesion (kPa)		Frictional Angle (ϕ)		Unit Weight (kN/m ³)	Distribution
	Mean	COV	Mean	COV		
Sand- layer 1	0	----	38	---	19.5	----

Table 2. Soil properties of the second and third layers

Statement	Attribute	Distribution	Mean	Std. Dev	Rel. Min	Rel. Max
Clay- Layer 2	Cohesion (kPa)	Uniform	5.3	----	2	6
Clay- Layer 2	Friction Angle (ϕ)	Uniform	23	----	9	9
Clay- Layer 2	Unit Weight (kN/m ³)	Normal	19.5	9	1.5	1.5
Clay- Layer 3	Cohesion (kPa)	Uniform	7.2	----	1	3
Clay- Layer 3	Friction Angle (ϕ)	Uniform	20	----	9	9
Clay- Layer 3	Unit Weight (kN/m ³)	Normal	19.5	9	1.5	1.5

SECTION 5: IMPACT OF DATA SCATTERING IN SPACE-FILLING

To accurately execute the LS-SVM, using appropriate training data processed by “support vectors” is the key. As a result, producing correct training data in quantity and quality is a challenging and pivotal task. According to Ji et al. (2017), less than 500 datasets for just two variables (C , Φ) are suitable for a general prediction. Here, the LHS for utilizing uniform distributions in soil variables of layers two and three (C , Φ) was used. This method is used for multivariate statistical distributions (Palisade Corporation 2009). Noticeably, this method is known as the most versatile one for computer experiments (Viana 2013). The uniform distribution assigns the same weight to each soil variable to be scattered. This action allows us to analyze the slope stability with more realistic information about the soil characteristics. Using normal/log-normal statistical distributions culminates in selecting the limited range of soil properties and cannot reflect the actual slope conditions. Space-filling has been performed in Fig. 3 in two different distributions for LS-SVM-trained models on the saturated slope.

Fig. 3a. Space-Filling for 300 datasets - Layer two (C, Φ), Fig. 3b. Space-Filling for 300 datasets- Layer three (C, Φ)

SECTION 6: DETERMINING OF TRAINING DATA SIZE

Since the LS-SVM is a data-driven model (in MATLAB), determining the number of training data is a vital issue. Figure 4 shows the trained LS-SVM performance from LHS with normal distributions. For $FS > 1$, the model predicts considerably well, but its operation degenerates exceedingly when FS is less than one. This is related to the normal distribution definition as the probability of a higher occurrence near the mean FS , which here is 1.198, and less in occurrence in other areas. Consequently, the success of the LS-SVM in predicting critical FS s ($FS < 1$) is not guaranteed. Conversely, the trained LS-SVM performance under uniform distributions in soil variables for the same problem is shown in Figs. 5 and 6, and the difference is noticeable. Utilizing uniform distributions enables the model to analyze soil stability with a more realistic perspective (Kang et al. 2015). In Figs. 5 and 6, the effect of training dataset number was tested in which 100 and 200 training datasets were generated, while soil variables were distributed uniformly. On the other hand, the 1900 and 1800 datasets (testing data), respectively, were perceived for normal and uniform distributions. Consequently, the more data, the better LS-SVM performed up to a certain number. According to the other studies, the number of training datasets between 10 to 15 times the dimensions of the soil characteristics is desirable. (Ji et al. 2017; Loepky et al. 2009).

Fig. 4a. Normal distribution (100 Training Data), Fig. 4b. Normal distribution (1900 Testing Data)

Fig. 5a. Uniform distribution (100 training data), Fig. 5b. Uniform distribution (1900 testing data)

Fig. 6a. Uniform distribution (200 training data), Fig. 6b. Uniform distribution (1800 testing data)

SECTION 7: CAPABILITY OF LS-SVM IN COMPUTING PROBABILITY OF FAILURE

Although using the multiple response surfaces method to examine PF in multi-layered slopes is more acceptable, determining both the number and form of these surfaces is arduous. Employing an ML model such as LS-SVM can appropriately handle this complexity of slope system stability (Ji et al. 2017). This study determines four different states to compare the PF derived by LS-SVM with other methods. See results in Table 2. This table compares the LS-SVM results under LHS with direct MCS subject to Spencer and Bishop Simplified models. Consequently, the desired performance of the proposed approach is achieved.

Table 3. Comparison of failure probabilities

Probabilistic Model	FS Model	PF (%)	FS
Direct MCS 30000	Spencer	15.95	1.15
LHS, LSSVM 200	Spencer	15.38	1.194
Direct MCS 30000	Bishop Simplified	31.21	1.069
LHS, LSSVM 200	Bishop Simplified	30.73	1.106

The PF-FS plot in Fig. 7 features the operation of the LS-SVM in each failure zone. Accordingly, the LS-SVM (red diagram) corresponds affirmatively with the traditional one (LEM) in most areas. The LS-SVM model needs 200 executions of training data here, while the LEM evaluation includes 30,000 runs. Moreover, there are some wrong predictions due to the limited size of training data, and the need for

accurate information related to layer one that is considered deterministic. As a result, since the model cannot consider the probabilistic distributions of the first layer (sand) in analysis, the failure modes captured in this layer could not be trained by the LS-SVM. In other words, if the correct slope information is not given to the LS-SVM by training data, the increased computational effort and size of the testing data cannot boost the system's accuracy on stability prediction.

Fig. 7. The Comparison of saturated slope failure probability in probabilistic (LS-SVM) and deterministic (Spencer) methods for ACADS slope.

SECTION 8: SUMMARY

The research reported in this paper is summarized as follows: The first and most obvious contribution that probabilistic modeling has made to geotechnical engineering is to make it possible to consider the PF in evaluating the failure slopes. The application of LS-SVM combined with Latin Hypercube Sampling as an ML method was presented to assess the stability of a multi-layered saturated slope. A typical multi-layered slope example was used to validate the slope stability modeling by the LS-SVM. Furthermore, the produced datasets subject to uniform and normal distributions were compared. The findings showed that the uniform distributions presented more accurate, realistic, and comprehensive information about the soil characteristics, specifically in multi-failure slopes. Then, the produced datasets by uniform distributions were utilized in the LS-SVM approach. 10% of these datasets were considered for training, and the rest as testing datasets. The relation between soil properties as input (γ , C , Φ) and FS as output were taught to LS-SVM using training data. Then, the LS-SVM generated **Estimated FSs** which were compared to the FSs of testing datasets (Fig. 7). Finally, a comparison between the PF derived from the LS-SVM results and Spencer and Bishop's Simplified methods was carried out as shown in Table 3.

SECTION 9: CONCLUSION

The stability of a saturated soil slope was evaluated by the LS-SVM method. The findings are as follows:

- The samples' scale in the LS-SVM procedure decreases compared to the LEM method, which reduces the computational time and cost potentially, while maintaining the prediction accuracy.

- Applying uniform distribution within cohesion and friction angle improves recognizing the FS and the PF of multi-failure slopes in LS-SVM. Consequently, it ends up with a better understanding and prediction of soil slope failures.
- An acceptable degree of similarity was found in the FS-PF chart between the traditional method LEM and the LS-SVM method in probabilistic evaluation of soil slope failure (Fig. 7).
- The LS-SVM analysis highly depends on the degree of uncertainty related to the soil strength parameters, which substantially impacts the FS-PF predictions. Consequently, is highly recommended that all slope layers' characteristics are used within their probabilistic distributions; otherwise, inaccurate results are anticipated. Moreover, using field and laboratory test data is highly recommended for the future research to be used as training data to compare such ML outcomes with them as an acceptable benchmark.

REFERENCE

1. Alidadi, N., Pezeshk, SH. 2024. Ground-Motion Model for Small-to-Moderate Potentially Induced Earthquakes Using an Ensemble Machine Learning Approach for CENA. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 0037-1106.
2. Bennett, K.P., and Campbell, C. 2000. Support vector machines: Hype or hallelujah?. *ACM SIGKDD Explorations Newsletter*, 2(2) 1–13.
3. Duncan, J.M. 1996. State of the art: Limit equilibrium and finite element analysis of slopes. *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, 122(7) 577–596.
4. Giam, P.S.K., and Donald, I.B. 1989. Example problems for testing soil slope stability programs. Monash University. Department of Civil Engineering, Report No. 8/1989, Monash Univ., Clayton, VIC, Australia.
5. Goh, SH. 2007. Support vector machines: their use in geotechnical engineering as illustrated using seismic liquefaction data. *Computers and Geotechnics*, 34(5) 410–421.
6. Goh, A. T.C., and Kulhawy, F.H. 2003. Neural network approach to model the limit state surface for reliability analysis. *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 40(6) 1235–1244.
7. Gori, M., and Tesi, A. 1992. On the problem of local minima in backpropagation. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 14(1) 76–86.
8. Griffiths D.V., Huang, J.S., and Fenton, G.A. 2012. Risk assessment in geotechnical engineering: stability analysis of highly variable soils. *Geotechnical Engineering State of the Art and Practice: Keynote Lectures from GeoCongress 2012*, 78–101.
9. Hakim, W.L., Rezaie, F., Nur, A.S., Panahi, M., Khosravi, KH., Lee, CH.W., and Lee, S. 2022. Convolutional neural network (CNN) with metaheuristic optimization algorithms for landslide susceptibility mapping in Icheon, South Korea. *Journal of Environmental Management.*, 305, 114367.
10. Hoang, N.D., Pham, A.D. 2016. Hybrid artificial intelligence approach based on metaheuristic and machine learning for slope stability assessment: A multinational data analysis. *Expert Systems with Applications.*, 46, 60-68.
11. Ji, J., Zhang, Ch., Gui, Y., Qing, L., and Kodikara, J. 2017. New Observations on the Application of LS-SVM in Slope System Reliability Analysis. *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 31(2).
12. Kang, F., Han, S., Salgado, R., and Li, J. 2015. System probabilistic stability analysis of soil slopes using Gaussian process regression with Latin hypercube sampling. *Computers and Geotechnics*, 63, 13–25.
13. Kang, F., and Li, J. 2016. Artificial bee colony algorithm optimized support vector regression for system reliability analysis of slopes. *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 30(3).
14. Loepky, J.L., Sacks, J., and Welch, W.J. 2009. Choosing the sample size of a computer experiment: A practical guide. *Technometrics*, 51(4) 366–376.
15. Lü, Q., Chan, C.L., and Low, B. K. 2012. Probabilistic evaluation of ground-support interaction for deep rock excavation using artificial neural network and uniform design. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 32, 1–18.

16. Maalouf, M., Khoury, N., and Trafalis, T.B. 2008. Support vector regression to predict asphalt mix performance. *International journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in Geomechanics*, 32(16) 1989–1996.
17. Pal, M., and Deswal, S. 2010. Modelling pile capacity using Gaussian process regression. *Computers and Geotechnics*, 37(7–8), 942–947.
18. Palisade Corporation. 2009. Guide to using @RISK: Risk analysis and simulation add-in for Microsoft® Excel. Ithaca, NY.
19. Rasmussen, C.E., and Williams, C.K.I. 2005. Gaussian processes for machine learning. The MIT Press, Cambridge, MA.
20. Sakellariou, M., and Ferentinou, M. 2005. A study of slope stability prediction using neural networks. *Geotechnical and Geological Engineering*, 23(4), 419–445.
21. Samui, P. 2008. Support vector machine applied to settlement of shallow foundations on cohesionless soils. *Computers and Geotechnics*, 35(3) 419–427.
22. Samui, P., Lansivaara, T., and Bhatt, M. 2013. Least square support vector machine applied to slope reliability analysis. *Geotechnical and Geological Engineering*, 31(4), 1329–1334.
23. Suykens, J. A. K., De Brabanter, J., Lukas, L., and Vandewalle, J. 2002b. Weighted least squares support vector machines: Robustness and sparse approximation. *Neurocomputing*, 48(1–4), 85–105.
24. Suykens J.A.K, Lukas, L., Van Dooren, P., De Moor, B., Vandewalle, J. 1999. Least squares support vector machine classifiers: a large-scale algorithm. *European Conference on Circuit Theory and Design, ECCTD*. Vol. 99. Citeseer.
25. Suykens, J.A., Van Gestel, T., De Brabanter, J., De Moor, B., and Vandewalle, J. 2002a. Least squares support vector machines. World Scientific, Singapore. Book
26. Vapnik, V. 2000. The nature of statistical learning theory. Springer, New York, 314. Book
27. Viana, F.A. 2013. Things you wanted to know about the Latin hypercube design and were afraid to ask. 10th World Congress on Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization. Vol. 19. No. 24.05, Orlando, FL.
28. Xue, J.F., Gavin, K. 2007. Simultaneous determination of critical slip surface and minimum reliability index for earth slopes. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, 133(7) 878–86.
29. Youssef, A.H., Pourghasemmi, H.R. 2021. Landslide susceptibility mapping using machine learning algorithms and comparison of their performance at Abha Basin, Asir Region, Saudi Arabia. *Geoscience Frontiers*. 12(2) 639-655.
30. Zhao, H.-B. 2008. Slope reliability analysis using a support vector machine. *Computers and Geotechnics*, 35(3) 459–467.